

AWARENESS ABOUT CONSUMER RIGHTS AMONG SCHOOL PUPILS IN TBILISI**Vakhtang Caraia***Professor, Grigol Robakidze University***Tengiz Taktakishvili***Professor, Grigol Robakidze University***Slava Petelava***Associate Professor, Grigol Robakidze University***Nino Sachaleli***Assistant, Grigol Robakidze University***Nino Kobalia***Student, Grigol Robakidze University***Abstract**

This study delves into the level of consumer rights awareness among Tbilisi school students. By analyzing factors influencing this awareness, the research identifies a significant knowledge gap, particularly in areas like product composition, complaint filing, and online shopping security. To address this, the study recommends integrating consumer education into the school curriculum, emphasizing interactive learning methods and real-world applications. Additionally, collaborations with consumer protection organizations and universities can enhance the effectiveness of these initiatives. By empowering young people with consumer rights knowledge, we can foster a more informed and responsible consumer society in Georgia.

Keywords: Consumer rights, consumer education, youth awareness, consumer protection, economic literacy, social responsibility.

Introduction

Consumer rights are an important foundation of modern society, ensuring that people are treated fairly and ethically in the marketplace and protecting them from fraud, dangerous products and unethical practices. These rights are vital to protecting private interests, promoting fair competition, raising product standards and increasing consumer confidence. Despite their undeniable relevance, knowledge of consumer rights varies significantly across different groups, particularly among younger generations. This disparity raises a critical question: are young members of society well prepared to navigate the complexities of the market and protect themselves from potential exploitation? In an ever-changing global marketplace, disseminating information about basic consumer rights is more important than ever. Schoolchildren are a particularly important group in this regard, as they represent the next generation of self-sufficient consumers. These young people will soon face barriers in making purchasing decisions, obtaining reliable information and combating unfair practices in an increasingly complex marketplace. By raising awareness of consumer rights during their formative years, society can prepare them to make informed decisions, resist unethical behavior and contribute to a culture of accountability, fairness and transparency.

Consumer protection is a critical issue worldwide, especially during the transition to a market economy. Market mechanisms do not provide effective protection against unfair competition and monopolistic behavior. Consumers in Georgia, as in other countries of the former Soviet Union, have historically been deprived of their rights due to the lack of legislation or an appropriate institutional framework. In 1996, Georgia adopted the Law on the Protection of Consumer Rights, which created the legislative framework for the protection of

consumer rights. However, in 2005, the law was declared illegal, which led to the abolition of the subordinate legislation necessary for the implementation of the law and the obligation of the executive branch to coordinate antitrust acts adopted to protect consumer rights. This led to the exclusion of Article 153 from the Code of Administrative Offenses of Georgia, which provided for administrative sanctions for violations of trade legislation (Petelava, 2015).

In 1995-2005, international experts made a significant contribution to improving Georgia's antimonopoly policy, especially in the area of consumer protection. These specialists, including American experts from the Center for Economic Policy and Reforms in Georgia, Professor Terry Berguen from the University of Leuven and Belgian experts, trained personnel on market mechanisms and consumer protection. The country lacked a unified consumer protection policy and effective mechanisms, which requires the exchange of experience with industrialized countries, especially the European Union. This problem has become even more urgent with the repeal of the Georgian Law "On the Protection of Consumer Rights". The UN General Assembly resolutions 39/248 and 151 on consumer protection are also important in addressing consumer rights issues. These resolutions establish a set of principles and standards for regulating restrictive business practices and call on governments to develop, strengthen or maintain measures to prohibit harmful conduct that may affect consumers (Petelava, 2015).

Consumer protection practices vary across developed European countries. In France the Directorate-General of the French Ministry of the Economy is responsible for competition, consumer protection and advertising regulation. In the United Kingdom, local authorities implement consumer protection legislation,

while the Office of Fair-Trading sets consumer policy but does not exercise powers. In some countries, such as Australia, restrictive business practices and competition laws are inextricably linked, with the same authority overseeing and enforcing their application. In some countries, the government oversees both competition and consumer protection through a single agency, although enforcement agencies exist separately. In contrast, the United States lacks a single, comprehensive body of law that regulates the quality of goods and services and the rights of consumers and sellers. Contract law, federal statutes, rules and regulations, interpretations by federal government agencies and actions by various state and municipal law enforcement agencies contain consumer protection principles. In the United States, federal agencies such as the Federal Trade Commission, the Consumer Product Safety Commission, the Food and Drug Administration, the Food Safety and Inspection Service, the Trademark and Patent Office, the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, the Federal Communications Commission and the Securities and Exchange Commission protect consumer rights. Other government agencies that regulate the banking industry include the Office of the Financial Conduct Authority, the Office of the Comptroller of the Treasury, the Federal Reserve and the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (Petelava, 2015).

This study examines the level of consumer rights awareness in Tbilisi, a dynamic and diverse city in Georgia. The study aims to determine how successfully consumer rights education has been integrated into the school curriculum and its effectiveness in shaping young people's attitudes by analyzing their knowledge and attitudes.

In addition, the article examines the sources through which students learn about consumer rights. These may include formal educational programmes, parental supervision, media influences and personal experiences. It also considers the challenges educators and policy makers face in incorporating consumer rights into educational programmes and the wider social implications of providing such knowledge to young people. The study thus illustrates the essential connection between education, social values and consumer culture. In addressing these issues, this study highlights the important role of education in preparing young people to navigate an increasingly consumer-driven world with confidence and responsibility. It advocates for the inclusion of comprehensive consumer education in school curricula to equip students with the skills needed to succeed in today's interconnected and competitive marketplace. Finally, the data demonstrates that ensuring a deep understanding of consumer rights among the younger generation is both a personal benefit and a societal imperative, leading to a fairer, more transparent and informed global economy.

Literature review

In recent years, scholars and policymakers have focused much attention on understanding consumer rights knowledge, which is considered a vital component of economic and civic literacy. This section re-

views the existing literature on consumer rights awareness, focusing on its importance, the role of education and the variables that determine its prevalence among young people.

Consumer rights are essential to ensure ethical business practices and protect people from exploitation. Kotler and Armstrong (2018) highlight that consumer rights not only protect people, but also promote fair trading practices, improve product quality and foster economic trust. Consumer International (2020) argues that increased awareness leads to informed decision-making by empowering consumers to challenge unethical behavior and hold firms accountable. However, many studies have identified gaps in consumer understanding, particularly among young people who are increasingly engaging in commerce through both traditional and digital platforms.

Educational institutions play an important role in promoting consumer rights. Formal education provides an opportunity to impart the knowledge and skills needed to deal with complex consumer situations. According to Grunert and Wills (2007), including consumer education in the school curriculum helps students understand concepts such as product safety, ethical consumption and dispute resolution. Similarly, the OECD (2019) argues that early consumer education is correlated with higher levels of economic literacy and responsible consumer behavior in adulthood.

In Tbilisi, Georgia, consumer education programmes are still at an early stage. The Ministry of Education of Georgia (2021) has emphasized the inclusion of consumer awareness programmes in the school curriculum to meet international standards. However, few studies have examined the effectiveness of these initiatives or students' awareness of them.

Family, media coverage and access to digital information influence young people's awareness of consumer rights. A study by Moschis and Churchill (1978) found that parental advice has a major impact on children's understanding of their rights and responsibilities as consumers. Many of the recent research papers highlights the growing importance of social media and online platforms as key sources of information for young people. These sites can be both helpful and harmful, providing real-time updates on consumer issues, while sometimes spreading misinformation.

Despite its importance, increasing the knowledge of consumer rights among students presents various challenges. Despite many global studies on awareness of consumer rights, there are few studies specifically focused on school students in Tbilisi. Most of the existing studies either focus on adolescents or take a broad approach to consumer education in Georgia. There is no data on the exact tactics Tbilisi schools use to teach these concepts, their success and how cultural and economic factors affect students' knowledge.

The available literature highlights the critical need for awareness of consumer rights, as well as the role of education in promoting responsible consumer behavior among youth. However, there are significant gaps, especially in knowing how students in Tbilisi interact with these concepts. The purpose of this study is to fill these gaps by analyzing the current level of awareness

among Tbilisi school students about consumer rights, studying the factors affecting their knowledge and identifying the potential for improving educational programs in this field.

The study of consumer awareness has received much attention worldwide due to the increasing complexity of the consumer environment and the critical importance of making informed decisions. Consumer education serves as a foundation for equipping consumers with the knowledge and skills needed to ethically navigate the marketplace. This section examines global strategies, approaches and frameworks for promoting knowledge about consumer rights, with a focus on youth education.

The concept of consumer rights has evolved in response to the challenges posed by globalization and mass production. Consumer rights ensure fair treatment in transactions, protect consumers from fraud and encourage ethical consumption. However, global surveys show that young consumers are often the least aware of their rights, despite their growing purchasing power and complex digital markets. International institutions such as the United Nations emphasize the need for consumer education. The UN Guidelines on Consumer Protection (updated in 2015) emphasize the need for youth-oriented educational initiatives to create a generation of responsible consumers. Countries such as Finland, Singapore and Australia have effectively integrated consumer education into their school curricula, exemplifying global best practice.

In many countries, consumer education is integrated into larger courses such as economics, civics and social sciences. For example, Australia's National Consumer and Financial Literacy Framework sets broad requirements for schools that link consumer education to practical skills such as budgeting, understanding contracts and internet safety. Similarly, in South Korea, consumer rights are a formal part of the secondary school curriculum, with an emphasis on practical applications such as dispute resolution and fraud prevention (OECD, 2019).

Modern educational methods emphasize interactive and experiential learning to increase student engagement and retention.

In contrast, some countries use a project-based strategy. For example, in Canada, students are tasked with developing awareness campaigns or studying real-life examples of consumer rights violations. These strategies promote critical thinking and a deeper understanding of the subject.

With the growth of e-commerce and digital marketplaces, online tools have become important in educating consumers about their rights. The EU's Consumer Classroom website provides teachers with resources to teach students about internet safety, advertising literacy and consumer law. These digital resources promote accessibility and allow educators to tailor content for different age groups.

Despite progress, the global effort faces significant challenges. The inclusion of consumer education in school curricula often competes with other academic priorities, resulting in a lack of time and resources for

the subject. In addition, cultural and economic disparities affect the success of educational programs.

Njuguna, Oloko, Oyugi (2014). examined the relationship between knowledge of consumer rights and consumerism in Nakuru County using methodologies such as Pearson correlation and linear regression analysis to analyze data collected from 400 households. This study provides a practical example of how simple regression analysis can be used to study influence of awareness on consumer behavior.

According to Gvenetadze (2019), the level of consumer education in Georgia is low compared to other EU member states due to legal gaps and lack of attention from the government and corporate sector. Georgia should urgently restore and implement the original version of the draft law "On Consumer Rights Protection" to improve the quality of education. Georgia can also follow the example of Hungary, which has effectively implemented consumer education programs. One of the important programs is Teaching and Learning for a Sustainable Future, which is aimed at students, teachers and consumer education professionals. Georgia's accession to the UN allows it to expand its cooperation with the UN and participate in this training program, effectively implementing the law on consumer rights protection. Research shows that professional orientation is key for youngster's future carrier planning (Kvirkvaia et al., 2018).

Danilanea and Marzano (2013) researched the relationship between social learning theories and the development of sustainable education, focusing on social, economic, environmental and cultural factors. They suggested that the content of consumer education in primary schools should be revised using theories of mentioned factors to improve the quality of life of students as consumers.

Bashir, Khan and Khan (2023) examined the relationship between consumer education and consumer protection laws, highlighting the need to educate consumers about their rights and responsibilities. It examines how consumer protection laws have evolved and how consumer education can contribute to consumer protection. The study also examines how technology and digital platforms are influencing consumer education, highlighting the importance of personalized approaches in the digital age.

Todua and Jashi (2018) discuss the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the importance of good nutrition for public health. Their study highlights the role of social marketing in solving social problems, as well as the importance of promoting activities in the agricultural and food industries. However, the introduction and promotion of healthy eating in Georgia remains a challenge due to the preference of low-quality food and low-income consumers for cheap products. Key solutions include research on consumer behavior towards good eating, focusing on interest, awareness and perception. The study also examines the impact of demographic characteristics on these variables.

Todua (2018) studied the role of healthy eating in food security and consumer sustainability, focusing on consumer knowledge and perception. According to

market research, age, education and money influence food awareness and subsequent purchase decisions.

Based on international best practices, Georgia can benefit from a hybrid strategy that combines formal education, experiential learning and digital resources. While Georgian youth learn consumer rights through informal channels such as family and media, a structured curriculum can provide consistency and depth of knowledge.

In addition, the use of regional case studies can make teaching more informative and effective. Students can, for example, investigate consumer disputes in Tbilisi markets or investigate the effects of online commerce in Georgia. Partnerships with consumer protection organizations and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) can expand the scope and quality of these programs.

Although research on knowledge of consumer rights is growing worldwide, research focused on school children, especially in transition countries such as Georgia, is limited. Most current research focuses on adult clients or broad economic knowledge. Future research should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of different teaching approaches in different settings, especially in cities like Tbilisi.

In addition, longitudinal studies could examine the long-term effects of consumer education on youth purchasing habits and economic activity. Understanding these trends can help develop more targeted and effective treatments.

In recent years, there has been a trend among young people towards entrepreneurial risk-taking, but this is insignificant compared to what can actually improve the country's image. Funds and business angels have been formed in the country, which are trying to invest in promising companies with global potential (Taktakishvili et al, 2024). This fact can contribute to the young generations' awareness about the consumer rights as well.

Global literature emphasizes the need for awareness of consumer rights and identifies various methods of educating young people. Best practices from Finland, South Korea and Australia emphasize the importance of formal education, interactive learning and digital technologies to develop a strong understanding

of consumer rights. For Georgia, incorporating these ideas into the local context in solving existing problems will significantly improve the effectiveness of consumer education among school pupils. This study aims to add to this growing debate by assessing the current state of consumer rights awareness in Tbilisi and recommending areas for development.

Methodology

We conducted the study among students of Tbilisi public schools and its goal was to identify what factors affect the level of awareness of Tbilisi school students about consumer rights. In order to obtain a homogeneous population and sample, only 11th graders were selected. Students had to answer ten questions on a five-point Likert scale. The questions corresponded to variables, one dependent (their own level of awareness of consumer rights) and 9 independent variables.

A total of 79 students from Tbilisi schools participated in the study.

Regression analysis was used to process the results of the study. The variables in the model were as follows:

- y - Level of awareness of students about consumer rights
- x1 - General information obtained from the Internet
- x2 - Information about the suitability of the product
- x3 - Information about the composition of the product
- x4 - Information about filing a complaint against the manufacturing company
- x5 - Information about returning or exchanging the product
- x6 - Information about regulations when purchasing the product remotely
- x7 - Information about the company's security policy
- x8 - Information about website security rules
- x9 - Information about warranty service

The study identified the factors that have the greatest impact on raising the level of awareness of schoolchildren about consumer rights.

Table 1.

Regression analysis

Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0.718514							
R Square	0.516263							
Adjusted R	0.452239							
Standard Error	0.763522							
Observations	78							
ANOVA								
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F			
Regression	9	42.30709	4.700787	8.063582	5.06E-08			
Residual	68	39.64163	0.582965					
Total	77	81.94872						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	0.86627	0.489022	1.771432	0.08097	-0.10956	1.842099	-0.10956	1.842099
x1	0.04595	0.094621	0.485615	0.628801	-0.14286	0.234763	-0.14286	0.234763
x2	-0.08554	0.096879	-0.88301	0.380343	-0.27886	0.107774	-0.27886	0.107774
x3	0.240784	0.094312	2.55305	0.012927	0.052587	0.428982	0.052587	0.428982
x4	0.255743	0.093726	2.728638	0.008087	0.068717	0.44277	0.068717	0.44277
x5	0.087158	0.087201	0.999504	0.321094	-0.08685	0.261165	-0.08685	0.261165
x6	0.126508	0.103493	1.222389	0.225781	-0.08001	0.333025	-0.08001	0.333025
x7	-0.00116	0.073314	-0.01589	0.987369	-0.14746	0.14513	-0.14746	0.14513
x8	0.070115	0.086737	0.808365	0.4217	-0.10297	0.243195	-0.10297	0.243195
x9	0.153227	0.090882	1.685993	0.096381	-0.02813	0.33458	-0.02813	0.33458

Source: Authors' calculations

Regression analysis showed that the level of awareness of schoolchildren about consumer rights is influenced by two independent variables in the model: x3 - information about the composition of the product and x4 - information about filing a complaint against the manufacturing company. It seems that students are most often exposed to this type of information and based on these issues, they deepen their knowledge of consumer rights. The regression analysis did not reveal any connections between the other independent variables in the model and the dependent variable. Accordingly, it can be said as a recommendation that it is necessary to implement more active information campaigns in those directions, the corresponding variables of which, according to the model, do not affect the level of awareness of schoolchildren.

The explanatory power of the model is acceptable, because according to the model, the variables present there explain the dependent variable by 45 percent. However, a certain limitation of the model is that it does not take into account the remaining variables. Some limitations may also exist in that the responses to these questions were based on students' perceptions and there may be elements of subjective assessment here.

Before conducting the regression analysis, a multicollinearity test was performed to rule out potential relationships between the independent variables. The test showed that there were no significant relationships between the independent variables and all of them could be retained in the model.

Table 2.

Multicollinearity test

	x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x7	x8	x9
x1	1								
x2	0.263296	1							
x3	0.343702	0.494994	1						
x4	0.39978	0.283485	0.334289	1					
x5	0.250425	0.409237	0.287488	0.431726	1				
x6	0.48577	0.427242	0.437493	0.443493	0.513566	1			
x7	0.20856	0.264541	0.222901	0.243796	0.26904	0.342328	1		
x8	0.350948	0.452088	0.507637	0.413164	0.435907	0.516212	0.516421	1	
x9	0.088373	0.180458	0.073294	0.263316	0.408522	0.328553	0.16909	0.198319	1

Source: Authors' calculations.

The study reveals a significant gap in the understanding of consumer rights among Tbilisi students and suggests targeted educational interventions to address this gap. Based on feedback from participants, a number of methods emerged as potential ways to raise awareness of consumer rights among students, consistent with global best practices in civic education and consumer protection. This includes structured projects,

interactive learning sessions and a greater emphasis on hands-on learning.

The participants suggested starting projects that would involve schoolchildren in the process of raising awareness. Organizing informational meetings and training sessions was highlighted as a critical step in establishing credibility and competence with industry experts. Such events not only teach students about consumer rights, but also allow them to share this

knowledge with their friends, creating a ripple effect that extends beyond the classroom.

A general recommendation was to develop links between schools and universities. Such collaboration can provide an interdisciplinary approach that combines academic knowledge with practical application. Workshops, seminars or experiential learning programs simulating consumer scenarios can be part of collaborative projects. Schools can provide students with a better understanding of consumer rights and responsibilities by using the resources and expertise of higher education institutions.

Participants enthusiastically supported the inclusion of hands-on activities and civic education in the school curriculum. Hands-on learning, such as simulated shopping or hands-on research, can help students understand complex concepts more clearly. Meanwhile, adding consumer rights topics to civics lectures emphasizes their importance in democratic participation and ethical consumption, encouraging students to consider these rights as an integral part of their role as informed citizens.

The respondents' enthusiasm for participating in and implementing various projects indicates a strong case for community-based initiatives. Using this motivation, schools can create student-led support groups or clubs dedicated to raising awareness of consumer rights. Such platforms can act as incubators for leadership and innovation, where students are actively involved in creating and implementing awareness campaigns.

To maintain sustainability, policymakers and educators should explore the possibility of integrating consumer education into broader educational curricula. This can be achieved by:

- Preparing of age-appropriate learning materials.
- Establishing an alliance with consumer protection authorities.
- Implementing teacher training programs to provide educators with the necessary skills to effectively present this information.

By addressing these components, the study highlights the importance of a comprehensive and interactive approach to consumer education that ensures young people gain the knowledge and tools they need to navigate the complexities of today's consumer marketplace.

Conclusion

This study shows a significant gap in consumer rights understanding among Tbilisi students, highlighting the critical need for targeted interventions to equip youth with important consumer knowledge and skills. The results indicate that educational activities should be inclusive, interactive and in line with global best practices in consumer protection and civic education.

Community-initiated projects and trainings are crucial to address this gap, as participants emphasized the need for professional engagement and participatory methods. Such projects not only convey important messages, but also inspire students to actively participate in

awareness campaigns, creating a peer-centered educational approach that extends beyond the classroom. These programs can help students develop leadership and responsibility by embedding consumer education in a broader framework of ethical and democratic participation.

Cooperation between schools and universities was established as an additional important strategy. Schools can use the knowledge and resources of higher education institutions to organize joint workshops, experiential learning programs and case study-based workshops. This coordinated effort will provide students with a realistic and comprehensive understanding of consumer rights, improving their ability to effectively solve real-world problems.

Integrating consumer education into the curriculum is an important step forward. Participants particularly strongly recommended hands-on learning, such as simulations and mock purchases, which allow students to apply theoretical information to the real world. In addition, the inclusion of consumer rights in citizenship education emphasizes its importance as a foundation for democratic participation, enabling students to see themselves as knowledgeable, empowered citizens.

Participant commitment to leadership and participation in such activities demonstrates the school community's willingness to embrace a participatory structure. Schools can build on this momentum by creating student-led consumer advocacy groups or clubs. These platforms will be hubs for creativity and collaboration, allowing students to design and implement awareness campaigns, thereby increasing their impact.

To ensure these efforts continue, the report suggests a collaborative strategy involving educators, legislators and consumer advocacy organizations. This includes creating age-appropriate learning materials, implementing teacher training programs and establishing school-industry partnerships. By incorporating consumer education into the curriculum, institutions can better equip students to navigate the complexities of today's consumer landscape with confidence, resilience and ethical awareness. Finally, this study highlights the transformative potential of a comprehensive, interactive approach to consumer education. These efforts can help create a more informed and responsible society by providing students with the knowledge and tools they need to advocate for themselves and promote a just economy.

This research highlights the need to equip Tbilisi school students with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate an increasingly complex market. The results show that certain types of information, such as knowledge of product components and the ability to file complaints against manufacturers, have a significant impact on school students' awareness of consumer rights. These results highlight the need for targeted educational interventions to address knowledge gaps and provide a better understanding of consumer rights.

International approaches demonstrate the importance of integrating consumer education into school curricula through formal education, experiential learning and digital resources. Countries such as Finland, South Korea and Australia have developed effective

systems that can serve as a model for Tbilisi schools. Localized case studies, participatory methods and collaboration with non-governmental and consumer organizations can help strengthen these initiatives.

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